

The Effect of Bosu Ball Usage on Some Physical Fitness Parameters in 5-6 Year-Old Children Taking Gymnastics Classes¹

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the effects of Bosu ball usage on certain physical fitness parameters in 5-6-year-old children taking gymnastics classes. A total of 70 students (35 experimental group and 35 control group) from a kindergarten in Afyonkarahisar were selected using a simple random sampling method. Prior to the study, demographic information (height, weight, age) was collected from all children, and flexibility, standing long jump, vertical jump, leg strength, grip strength, and balance measurements were taken. The experimental group performed Bosu ball exercises for 12 weeks, three days per week, three sets in addition to their regular gymnastics training. To check for normal distribution of data, skewness-kurtosis values were assessed, and Levene's test and independent t-test were used to determine the equality of variances and differences between the groups. Additionally, a 2*2 ANOVA analysis was performed to examine the pre-test and post-test values of the experimental and control groups. The results showed that while there was a significant difference within the experimental group regarding anthropometric measurements, no statistically significant difference was observed between the groups in terms of pre-test and post-test values. Both the experimental and control groups showed significant improvements in flexibility, standing long jump, vertical jump, anaerobic power, leg strength, grip strength, and balance parameters, but the experimental group demonstrated greater improvements than the control group. The results can also be evaluated with different exercises to determine their contribution to physical fitness parameters and body composition in different ways.

Keywords: Bosu Ball, Physical Fitness, Physical health, Gymnastics

INTRODUCTION

Gymnastics, which is widely practiced in our country and is a sport suitable for children's developmental levels, can be started at an early age and plays an important role in the development of sports culture in children. The contribution of gymnastics to children's overall development has been proven in many scientific studies, and several studies have been conducted on encouraging children to engage in gymnastics. This sport has a unique characteristic that influences the mental, physical, and cognitive skills of people across all age groups.

Gymnastics requires high levels of flexibility, strength, endurance, coordination, and agility and works all muscle groups in the body (Mitchell et al., 2002).

The BOSU ball, invented by David Weck in 1999 (Badau et al., 2019), allows for various training programs, including endurance, flexibility, strength, and balance, for coaches and athletes. However, there is a noticeable gap in the literature regarding studies on Bosu ball exercises applied in gymnastics

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training, particularly concerning physical fitness parameters such as balance and flexibility, which are crucial for athletic performance.

The term "BOSU" stands for "Both Sides Up," indicating that the ball can be used with either side up. It is a training device designed for balance training for active individuals. The ball is made of inflatable rubber material resembling a half-split Swiss ball, with a durable plastic base. The user can perform exercises both in a horizontal position for core workouts and in a vertical position for various exercises. The dome-shaped rubber side or the flat plastic side can be used for balance and strength exercises (Yaggie & Campbell, 2006).

When David Weck developed the Bosu ball, he created a tool to improve coordination by increasing symmetrical strength in the human body. Asymmetry occurs when one side of the body is stronger than the other. The Bosu ball helps address this by strengthening the weaker side, enabling it to catch up with the stronger side. Using the Bosuball improves both brain balance (left and right) and body balance (Wing, 2014).

Studies have shown that physical activities positively affect anthropometric measurements and body weight in young children who are involved in sports. As a result, body composition improves, allowing children to reach better levels of physical fitness compared to their peers. This factor provides children who engage in sports at an early age with an advantage in terms of fine motor skills and cognitive abilities. Children who continue to engage in sports regularly demonstrate positive development in motor coordination and physical fitness levels according to their sports age (Opstoel et al., 2015).

Between the ages of 5 and 8, children's growth starts in the arms and continues with the elongation of the leg bones. There is no proportion between the organs at this stage. Coordination between small and large muscles has not yet fully developed. Coordination skills between large joints and muscles begin to develop. The smaller muscle groups develop, and children begin to move in a coordinated way (e.g., eye-hand coordination and wrist movements) with fine motor skills. Some children may experience postural and skeletal problems due to rapid growth in height (Güler, 2018).

Continual physical activity in children improves bone health, body composition, cardiovascular health, and muscle health, reduces the risk of depression, and increases the likelihood of children being healthier in adulthood. Therefore, considering the health benefits of physical activities and the negative aspects of sedentary lifestyles in children, physical fitness levels become even more critical (Alkan & Mutlu, 2020).

This study aims to improve flexibility, horizontal and vertical jump, anaerobic capacity, leg and back strength, hand grip strength, and balance skills through the use of a Bosu ball. The fact that this new training tool is still relatively new in the literature, and that most studies have been conducted in other sports and age groups, led us to undertake this study.

This study aims to examine the effects of Bosu ball usage on certain physical fitness parameters in 5-6-year-old children taking gymnastics classes at a kindergarten in Afyonkarahisar province.

METHOD

Methodology and Research Design: In this study, a pre-test and post-test control group measurement method was applied, which is one of the quantitative research methods. Consent forms were obtained from the children's families, and permission for the research was also obtained from the special education institution where the children are educated. In addition, an ethical committee decision was obtained from the Afyon Kocatepe University, Health Sciences Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee, dated 05.10.2022 and numbered 11. The study group consisted of 70 (n=35 experimental group – n=35 control group) 5-6-year-old students who took gymnastics classes at a kindergarten in Afyonkarahisar, selected through simple random sampling. At the beginning of the study, demographic information (height, weight, age) was collected from all children as a pre-test, and measurements of flexibility, standing long jump, vertical jump, leg strength, grip strength, and static

balance were taken. While the children in the control group performed regular gymnastics training, the students in the experimental group performed Bosu ball exercises in addition to their regular training for 12 weeks. The exercises were carried out three days a week (Monday, Wednesday, and Friday), with five prescribed exercises performed in three sets each. A 10-second rest was given between each exercise, and a 1-minute rest was provided between each set. Data was collected between January 1, 2023 and March 31, 2023.

Table 1. Training Protocol

Duration	Days	Exercises	Repetitions & Sets	Rest Interval
12 Weeks	Monday	Exercises 1. 2. 3. 4. 5	10 repetitions × 3 sets	1 min rest between sets
	Wednestay	Exercises 6. 7. 8. 9. 10	10 repetitions × 3 sets	1 min rest between sets
	Friday	Exercises 11. 12. 13. 14. 15	10 repetitions × 3 sets	1 min rest between sets

Data Measurement Tools: For the measurements of height and weight, a SECA brand scale was used. Flexibility was measured using the sit-and-reach test on a flexibility bench. For vertical jump measurements, an electronic TAKEI JAMP-MD Jump Meter was used. Leg strength was measured with a TAKEI BACK-D brand digital back-leg dynamometer. Grip strength was measured using a TAKEI GRIP-D hand dynamometer. For balance measurements, the Flamingo Balance Test was applied. Additionally, anaerobic power measurements were calculated using the formula $P = \sqrt{4.9(W)} \sqrt{D}$ (kg.m/s) based on body weight (W) and vertical jump distances (D) (Tamer, 1995).

Data Analysis: In this study, the research data showed a normal distribution with skewness and kurtosis values falling within the range of -1.5 to +1.5 (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). To determine whether the groups were equivalent in terms of variables, the pre-test mean scores of the measurements were compared. The Equality of Variance of the pre-test scores between the experimental and control groups was tested using Independent T-Test, while differences in the repeated measurements of normally distributed data were examined using Repeated Measures 2*2 ANOVA. Statistical analysis of the data obtained in this study was performed using SPSS 25.0 software. Initially, the mean and standard deviation values of the data were calculated, and a 95% confidence interval was chosen for the statistical analysis. Values below $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

Table 2. Equality of Variance of Pre-Test Scores Between Experimental and Control Groups (Independent T-Test)

Variables	Group	n	\bar{X}	Sd	F	p
Height (cm)	Experimental	35	111.29	5.04		
	Control	35	110.84	5.52		
Weight (kg)	Experimental	35	19.47	2.66	1.514	.953
	Control	35	19.51	2.99		
Body Mass Index(BMI) (kg/m ²)	Experimental	35	15.53	1.67	.141	.501
	Control	35	15.79	1.58		
Flexibility (cm)	Experimental	35	19.91	4.11	.020	.977
	Control	35	19.89	4.21		
Standing Long Jump (cm)	Experimental	35	76.20	13.49	.461	.963
	Control	35	76.06	12.12		
Vertical Jump (cm)	Experimental	35	11.40	3.05	4.921	.334
	Control	35	12.01	2.07		
	Experimental	35	32.58	4.65		

Pre-Test	Anaerobic Power (kg-m/sn)	Control	35	33.69	4.08	.333	.290
	Leg Strength (kg)	Experimental	35	20.78	.98		
		Control	35	20.70	.88	1.511	.703
	Grip Strength (Dominant Hand) (kg)	Experimental	35	7.49	1.52		
		Control	35	7.31	1.41	.112	.622
	Grip Strength (Non-Dominant Hand) (kg)	Experimental	35	6.96	1.37		
		Control	35	6.96	1.31	.053	.979
	Static Balance (Error Count)	Experimental	35	29.31	5.32	.443	.649
		Control	35	28.69	6.14		

According to Table 2, no significant difference was found between the pre-test scores of the experimental and control groups ($p > .05$). The analysis of the data supports the homogeneity of variances for both the experimental and control groups.

RESULTS

Table 3. Measurement Results of the Experimental and Control Groups (2x2 ANOVA)

Variables	Group	n	Pre-Test	Post-Test	Time		Group - Time	
			$\bar{X} \pm SD$	$\bar{X} \pm SD$	F (p)	η^2	F (p)	η^2
Height (cm)	Experimental	35	110.84 ± 5.04	112.50 ± 5.62	100.315*	.596	.007	.000
	Control	35	111.29 ± 5.52	112.99 ± 5.42				
Weight (kg)	Experimental	35	19.51 ± 2.99	20.29 ± 3.21	118.759*	.636	.431	.006
	Control	35	19.47 ± 2.66	20.35 ± 2.72				
Body Mass Index(BMI) (kg/m ²)	Experimental	35	15.79 ± 1.58	15.97 ± 1.74	8.92*	.116	1.574	.023
	Control	35	15.53 ± 1.67	15.97 ± 2.28				
Flexibility (cm)	Experimental	35	19.89 ± 4.21	21.97 ± 4.14	192.000*	.738	52.083*	.434
	Control	35	19.91 ± 4.11	20.57 ± 4.10				
Standing Long Jump (cm)	Experimental	35	76.06 ± 12.12	91.54 ± 13.90	207.177*	.753	37.323*	.354
	Control	35	76.20 ± 13.49	82.46 ± 15.09				
Vertical Jump (cm)	Experimental	35	12.01 ± 2.07	13.97 ± 2.05	174.208*	.719	27.138*	.285
	Control	35	11.40 ± 3.05	12.25 ± 3.17				
Anaerobic Power (kg-m/sn)	Experimental	35	33.69 ± 4.08	37.08 ± 4.09	210.501*	.756	14.169*	.172
	Control	35	32.58 ± 4.65	34.57 ± 4.95				
Leg Strength (kg)	Experimental	35	20.70 ± .88	22.81 ± 1.79	101.090*	.598	22.512*	.249
	Control	35	20.78 ± .98	21.54 ± 1.52				
Grip Strength (Dominant Hand) (kg)	Experimental	35	7.31 ± 1.41	8.13 ± 1.66	126.843*	.651	6.211*	.084
	Control	35	7.49 ± 1.52	8.01 ± 1.59				
	Experimental	35	6.96 ± 1.37	7.68 ± 1.37	140.295*	.674	4.703*	.065

Grip Strength (Non-Dominant Hand) (kg)	Control	35	6.96 ± 1.31	7.45 ± 1.56				
	Experimental	35	28.69 ± 6.14	16.20 ± 4.88				
Static Balance (Error Count)	Control	35	29.31 ± 5.32	24.49 ± 4.36	426.873*	.863	83.488*	.551
	Experimental	35	28.69 ± 6.14	16.20 ± 4.88				

As shown in Table 3, a statistically significant difference was found within groups in pre-test and post-test measurement values of height, body weight, and body mass index (BMI) ($p < .05$). According to the repeated-measures ANOVA, no statistically significant difference was observed between groups in pre-test and post-test measurement values of height, body weight, and body mass index ($p > .05$). However, the mean values of both the experimental and control groups increased from pre-test to post-test.

A statistically significant difference was identified between within-group measurements for the variables of flexibility, standing long jump, vertical jump, anaerobic power, leg strength, handgrip strength, and static balance ($p < .05$). In addition, statistically significant increases were observed between groups in flexibility, standing long jump, vertical jump, anaerobic power, leg strength, handgrip strength, and static balance measurements based on pre-test and post-test data ($p < .05$). Moreover, all mean values in both the experimental and control groups showed an increase from pre-test to post-test.

DISCUSSION and CONCLUSION

According to the findings obtained from the study, a significant difference was observed within the groups in terms of body weight, height, and body mass index values, whereas no significant difference was detected between the groups. In a study conducted by Okludil (2021) on adolescent female volleyball players, it was reported that Bosu exercises did not result in a significant increase in body mass index values between the experimental and control groups. Similarly, Güler (2018) stated that eight weeks of balance training performed with a Bosu ball in football players did not produce a notable difference in body fat percentage and body mass index values between the control and experimental groups. Additionally, in another study, it was reported that Bosu exercises applied to individuals attending fitness centers did not show a significant difference in pre-test and post-test parameters of the control group; however, significant differences were observed in body fat percentage and body weight variables in the experimental group's pre-test and post-test values (Uçar, 2020).

Comparable studies in the literature conducted on different groups also reveal varying results regarding the effects of Bosu training on body composition. Nevertheless, it may be stated that, in general, Bosu exercises do not exert a marked effect on changes in body composition. The within-group differences observed in this study may be associated with the developmental processes expected at the ages of the participating children.

In the present study, when the flexibility values were compared, a statistically significant difference was found both within the groups and between the groups. Kırıcı (2014), in an exercise program aimed at preventing anterior cruciate ligament injuries in male football players, incorporated Bosu ball exercises and reported a significant improvement in the flexibility measurements of the experimental group. Dilber et al. (2016), in their study investigating the effects of core exercises on performance-related physical fitness variables, also determined that flexibility values of the athletes showed a significant increase following Bosu exercises. Similarly, Koçak (2019) reported a significant difference in the sit-and-reach flexibility parameter in a study examining the effect of artistic gymnastics training on some physical fitness components in girls aged 7–9. In the present study, improvements were observed in both the experimental and control groups. However, when the magnitude of improvement was examined, the experimental group showed a greater level of progress. The more pronounced development observed in the experimental group appears to be attributable to the additional effect provided by Bosu ball exercises incorporated alongside gymnastics training.

In this study, a statistically significant difference was also found in the standing long jump values for both experimental and control groups based on the comparison of pre-test and post-test values within and between the groups. Aysan (2019), who investigated the effects of strength training with a Bosu ball for eight weeks in 14-year-old children playing football, reported that the intervention positively affected standing long jump performance. Okludil (2021) conducted an eight-week strength exercise and Bosu balance training program with adolescent female volleyball players aged 14–15 and observed a significant increase in standing long jump performance. Sinar (2017) likewise reported a notable improvement in standing long jump performance among female athletes aged 13–15 following Kangoo Jump training. In another study, Koca (2016) compared motor skills of boys and girls competing in trampoline and artistic gymnastics at the youth level and found that post-test values showed a significant improvement compared to pre-test scores, with artistic gymnasts showing higher standing long jump performance than the trampoline group for both sexes. The findings of the present research are consistent with those reported in the literature. Standing long jump is considered an indicator of explosive power, a physical attribute that can be improved through various training methods. It was observed that Bosu exercises performed in addition to gymnastics training contributed significantly to standing long jump performance.

In the present study, a statistically significant increase was observed in vertical jump measurements. Salot et al. (2020) reported that a six-week Bosu exercise program improved vertical jump height and single-leg jump distance in male football players. Similarly, Okludil (2021) found a significant difference between pre-test and post-test values for the vertical jump parameter in female volleyball players aged 14–16 after Bosu training. Boyacı and Bıyıklı (2018) reported that a 10-week core training program applied to football players aged 11–13 positively affected vertical jump performance in both the experimental and control groups. Findings from similar studies indicate that exercise programs incorporating Bosu training have a positive effect on vertical jump performance. The inclusion of stepping, jumping, and other leg-strength-oriented exercises in Bosu routines appears to have positively contributed to performance development.

In this study, a significant increase was also identified in anaerobic power values both within groups and between groups based on pre- and post-test comparisons. Atalay Güzel et al. (2022) reported that six weeks of core stabilization exercises performed with a Bosu ball led to a statistically significant improvement in anaerobic power performance in female volleyball players. In another study, Okludil (2021) concluded that eight weeks of Bosu exercises positively influenced anaerobic power performance in adolescent female volleyball players aged 14–16. Varol (2021) examined the effects of core training performed with BOSU-Swiss ball and without equipment on anaerobic power, body composition, selected blood parameters, and trunk extensor endurance in a study involving 30 volunteers. Participants were randomly assigned to three groups: Control Group (CG), Bosu-Swiss Ball Group (BSG), and Training Group (TG). After five weeks of training, significant differences were observed in trunk extension test scores and anaerobic power values in the training groups. In a separate study, Baynaz et al. (2017) investigated the effects of high-intensity interval training on anaerobic capacity and flexibility. They applied a Tabata-based high-intensity interval training program three times a week for six weeks to 20 sedentary women and reported improvements in anaerobic power parameters. Based on these studies, it may be suggested that training programs enhancing leg strength also naturally contribute to the improvement of anaerobic power.

In this study, a statistically significant increase was observed in leg strength measurements. Sarıkaya (2022) and Sarıkaya et al. (2023) reported that eight weeks of Bosu ball exercises resulted in a significant improvement in leg strength among female taekwondo athletes and basketball players. In a similar study, İşeri (2020) found that mini-trampoline exercises had a significant effect on leg strength, as one of the physical fitness parameters, in boys aged 11–12. In the present research, gymnastics training appeared to influence leg strength values in both the experimental and control groups. However, when the level of improvement was examined, the experimental group demonstrated a greater increase. This may be attributed to the additional effect generated by Bosu ball exercises performed alongside gymnastics training.

In the evaluation of handgrip strength, a statistically significant increase was identified both within and between the groups when pre-test and post-test measurements were compared. Previous studies with similar characteristics have reported that pilates, calisthenics, functional training, and educational play-based exercises improved handgrip strength (Erbaş, 2018; Pektaş, 2021; Kaya, 2023). The significant increase observed in the handgrip strength variable in this study aligns with findings reported in the relevant literature.

In the present study, it was determined that Bosu ball exercises positively improved balance. Tura (2023) reported that eight weeks of Bosu training had beneficial effects on the development of both dynamic and static balance in basketball players aged 15–16. Similarly, Bayrakdar et al. (2020) investigated the effect of ten weeks of Bosu-based exercises on static balance in tennis players aged 12–14 and found a statistically significant increase in static balance scores in the experimental group when pre- and post-test results were compared. Another study using Bosu balls, inflatable cushions, and inflatable discs reported a reduction in lower extremity asymmetry and a significant improvement in balance measurements in the experimental group (Sannicandro et al., 2014). Considering that balance is not only an essential component of daily life but also a foundational element in many sports disciplines, the findings of this study indicate that Bosu ball exercises conducted in addition to gymnastics training strengthen the hip and leg muscles and contribute to balance development.

In conclusion, while a significant difference was observed within groups in pre- and post-test anthropometric measurements following 12 weeks of Bosu ball training in addition to gymnastics classes among preschool children aged 5–6, no statistically significant difference was found between groups. For the variables of flexibility, standing long jump, vertical jump, anaerobic power, leg strength, handgrip strength, and balance, both the experimental and control groups demonstrated significant improvements from pre-test to post-test; however, the increases in the experimental group were found to be greater than those in the control group.

This study is limited to children aged 5–6 years who were taking gymnastics classes at a kindergarten located in the province of Afyonkarahisar in 2023. The novelty of this training tool (the BOSU ball) and its still limited representation in the literature, along with the fact that most existing studies have been conducted in different sports disciplines and across different age groups, indicate that this study may contribute to the field. By evaluating the results in combination with different types of exercises, it may be possible to determine the varying contributions of these practices to physical fitness parameters and body composition.

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